
On Carmichael numbers

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Abstract. A composite number n is called a Carmichael number if $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ for any integer a coprime with n .

Let n be a Carmichael number. By considering the subgroups E (resp. F) of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ whose elements \bar{a} satisfy the condition $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n}$ (resp. $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$), we first obtain a new criterion for a given integer to be a Carmichael number. Afterwards, alluding to a paper of Lehmer on strong Carmichael numbers,

we define the *really strong Carmichael numbers* to be the Carmichael numbers such that $F = (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ and show that this class of numbers is not empty. We then give different criteria for a given Carmichael number to be a really strong Carmichael number.

1 Introduction

In 1910, R. D. Carmichael [2] defined the arithmetic function $\lambda(n)$ by

$$\lambda(2) = \Phi(2) = 1, \quad \lambda(2^2) = \Phi(2^2) = 2,$$
$$\lambda(p^e) = \begin{cases} \Phi(p^e) = p^{e-1}(p-1) & \text{if } p \text{ is odd and } e \geq 1 \\ \frac{\Phi(2^e)}{2} = 2^{e-2} & \text{if } p = 2 \text{ and } e \geq 3 \end{cases}$$

and in general

$$\lambda(p_1^{e_1} \cdots p_r^{e_r}) = \text{lcm}(\lambda(p_1^{e_1}), \dots, \lambda(p_r^{e_r})).$$

Let $n \geq 2$ be an integer. It is easy to see that the exponent of the group $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ divides $\lambda(n)$. Indeed, even better than this divisibility property alone, the paper [2] proves equality. That is there exists an element of the group whose order is equal to $\lambda(n)$.

The famous Fermat's little theorem asserts that if p is a prime number, then for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\gcd(a, p) = 1$, we have $a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. The converse of this theorem is

false. Carmichael [3] gave the first counter-example, namely $n = 561 = 3 \times 11 \times 17$, so we are led to the following definition. A composite number n is called a *Carmichael number* if for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, we have $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$.

The known criteria for an integer to be a Carmichael number are summarized in the following result. Here $\sigma_p(n)$ denotes the sum of the digits of n in the basis p .

Theorem 1. *Let $n \geq 2$ be a composite number, then the following conditions are equivalent.*

- (i) n is a Carmichael number.
- (ii) n is square-free and any prime factor p of n satisfies the condition $p-1 \mid n-1$.
- (iii) $\lambda(n) \mid n-1$.
- (iv) n is square-free and for any prime factor p of n , we have $\sigma_p(n) \equiv 1 \pmod{p-1}$ and $\sigma_p(n) \geq p$, where $\sigma_p(n)$ denotes the sum of the digits of n in the numerical basis p .

The equivalence of (i) with (ii) (resp. (i) with (iii)) (resp. (i) with (iv)) are due to A. R. Korselt [8], R. D. Carmichael [3] and Kellner-Sandow [7] respectively.

In Corollary 1, a new criterion to recognize Carmichael numbers is given.

In [1] the authors proved that there are infinitely many Carmichael numbers.

Let n be a Carmichael number such that $n = p_1 \dots p_{r_1} p_{r_1+1} \dots p_{r_1+r_2}$ (*) with $v_2(p_i-1) < v_2(n-1)$ if and only if $1 \leq i \leq r_1$.

We consider the subgroups of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ defined by:

$$E = \left\{ \bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*, a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n} \right\} \text{ and}$$
$$F = \left\{ \bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*, a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n} \right\}$$

In Theorem 3 we determine E and F and then $|E|$ and $|F|$ using the factorization (*) of n .

In [11] D. H. Lehmer defined what he called a *strong Carmichael number* to be an odd composite integer n for which $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n}$ for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, that is $|E| = \varphi(n)$, and he showed, in that same paper, that these numbers do not exist. However, here, we show that the Carmichael numbers n for which $|F| = \varphi(n)$, which we call the *really strong Carmichael numbers*, form a non-empty class. In the last section, by using the type of factorization of a given Carmichael number n and the set $V = \left\{ \overline{a^{(n-1)/2}}, a \in \mathbb{Z}, \gcd(a, n) = 1 \right\}$, we give different criteria to determine whether n is a really strong Carmichael number or not.

2 Strong Carmichael numbers, Euler's criterion and Fermat's little theorem.

An odd composite number n for which $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n}$ for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, is called by D. H. Lehmer a strong Carmichael number. Here $\left(\frac{a}{n}\right)$ denotes the Jacobi symbol. If n is strong, then

$$\left(a^{(n-1)/2}\right)^2 \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)^2 \pmod{n} \equiv 1 \pmod{n},$$

hence n is a Carmichael number. For example for $n = 561$ which is the smallest Carmichael number, we have $2^{560/2} = 2^{280} \equiv -1 \pmod{561} \equiv \left(\frac{2}{561}\right) \pmod{561}$ and $5^{280} \equiv 67 \pmod{561} \not\equiv \pm 1 \pmod{561}$, hence 561 is not a strong Carmichael number. Indeed, in his paper, Lehmer proved that there exists no strong Carmichael number. This result of Lehmer proves the necessity part of the next theorem. The sufficiency of the condition is known as Euler's Criterion (see [4], Chap. 3, p. 67.)

Theorem 2. *Let $n \geq 2$ be an integer. Then $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n}$, for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, if and only if n is prime.*

In the following, we describe the group E (resp. F) whose elements $\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ satisfy the preceding condition of Lehmer: $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n}$ (resp. the condition: $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$), where n is a Carmichael number.

Let n be a Carmichael number,

$$E = \{\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*, a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \pmod{n}\} \quad \text{and}$$

$$F = \{\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*, a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}\},$$

then E and F are the kernels of the following morphisms

$$\alpha \quad \text{and} \quad \beta : (\mathbb{Z}n\mathbb{Z})^* \rightarrow (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$$

respectively, where

$$\alpha(\bar{a}) = \overline{a^{(n-1)/2} \left(\frac{a}{n}\right)} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta(\bar{a}) = \overline{a^{(n-1)/2}}.$$

These groups E and F will be called Euler's group and Fermat's group respectively.

Theorem 3. *Let n be a Carmichael number and let $n = p_1 \cdots p_{r_2} l_1 \cdots l_{r_1}$ be its factorization as a product of prime numbers, where*

$$\nu_2(p_i - 1) \leq \nu_2((n - 1)/2) \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, r_2$$

$$\nu_2(l_j - 1) = \nu_2(n - 1) \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r_1.$$

If $r_2 \neq 0$, then

$$E \simeq H \times \prod_{j=1}^{r_1} H_j \quad \text{and} \quad F \simeq \prod_{i=1}^{r_2} (\mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z})^* \times \prod_{j=1}^{r_1} H_j.$$

If $r_2 = 0$, then $r_1 = r$,

$$F = \prod_{j=1}^r H_j,$$

and

$$E = \begin{cases} \prod_{j=1}^r H_j & \text{if } r \text{ is even or,} \\ \{\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*, \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) = \dots = \left(\frac{a}{l_r}\right)\} & \text{if } r \text{ is odd,} \end{cases}$$

where

$$H_j = \{\bar{b} \in (\mathbb{Z}/l_j\mathbb{Z})^*, \left(\frac{b}{l_j}\right) = 1\}$$

for $j = 1, \dots, r_1$ and

$$H = \{\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/p_1 \cdots p_{r_2}\mathbb{Z})^*, \left(\frac{a}{p_1 \cdots p_{r_2}}\right) = 1\}.$$

Moreover, $(\mathbb{Z}/l_j\mathbb{Z})^* : H_j = 2$, $((\mathbb{Z}/p_1 \cdots p_{r_2}\mathbb{Z})^* : H) = 2$ and if $r_2 \geq 2$, then H may not be written as a direct product of the form $H = \prod_{i=1}^{r_2} U_i$, where U_i is a subgroup of $(\mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z})^*$ for $i = 1, \dots, r_2$. If $r_2 \neq 0$, then E is a subgroup of F of index 2. If $r_2 = 0$, then $E = F$ if r is even and F is a subgroup of E of index 2 if r is odd.

Proof. We will use repeatedly the following properties. Since $t - 1 \mid n - 1$ for any prime factor t of n , then for any $i \in \{1, \dots, r_2\}$ and any $j \in \{1, \dots, r_1\}$, we have $p_i - 1 \mid (n - 1)/2$ and $(n - 1)/2 \equiv (l_i - 1)/2 \pmod{l_i - 1}$. By Euler's criterion, this implies

$$a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i} \quad \text{and} \quad a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv a^{(l_j-1)/2} \pmod{l_j} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) \pmod{l_j},$$

for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. We consider two cases.

• **Case $r_2 \neq 0$.** For any $\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a} \in F &\Leftrightarrow a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) = 1 \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r_1 \\ &\Leftrightarrow a \pmod{l_j} \text{ is a square} \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r_1 \\ &\Leftrightarrow a + l_j\mathbb{Z} \in (\mathbb{Z}/l_j\mathbb{Z})^{*2} \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r_1, \end{aligned}$$

hence

$$F \simeq \prod_{i=1}^{r_2} (\mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z})^* \times \prod_{j=1}^{r_1} H_j,$$

where $H_j = (\mathbb{Z}/l_j\mathbb{Z})^{*2}$.

We now characterize E in this case. Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a} \in E &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \equiv a^{(n-1)/2} \pmod{n} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \equiv a^{(n-1)/2} \pmod{p_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \equiv a^{(n-1)/2} \pmod{l_j} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{p_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{p_{r_2}}\right) \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{l_{r_1}}\right) \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i} \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, r_2 \\ \text{and} \quad &\left(\frac{a}{p_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{p_{r_2}}\right) \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{l_{r_1}}\right) \equiv \left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) \pmod{l_j} \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r_1 \\ &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{p_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{p_{r_2}}\right) \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{l_{r_1}}\right) = 1 \\ \text{and} \quad &\left(\frac{a}{p_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{p_{r_2}}\right) \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{l_{r_1}}\right) = \left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r_1 \\ &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) = 1 \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{a}{p_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{p_{r_2}}\right) = 1 \\ &\Leftrightarrow \bar{a} \in H \times \prod_{j=1}^{r_1} H_j, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$H_j = \{\bar{b} \in (\mathbb{Z}/l_j\mathbb{Z})^*, \left(\frac{b}{l_j}\right) = 1\} \quad \text{and} \quad H = \{\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/p_1 \cdots p_{r_2}\mathbb{Z})^*, \left(\frac{a}{p_1 \cdots p_{r_2}}\right) = 1\}.$$

• **Case $r_2 = 0$.** Here, $r_1 = r$. The same reasoning as above shows that $F = \prod_{j=1}^r H_j$.

Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{a} \in E &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \equiv a^{(n-1)/2} \pmod{n} \\
 &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{n}\right) \equiv a^{(n-1)/2} \pmod{l_j} \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r \\
 &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{l_r}\right) \equiv \left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) \pmod{l_j} \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r \\
 &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{l_r}\right) = \left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, r \\
 &\Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) = \dots = \left(\frac{a}{l_r}\right) \quad \text{if } r \text{ is odd and} \\
 &\quad \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) = \dots = \left(\frac{a}{l_r}\right) = 1 \quad \text{if } r \text{ is even.}
 \end{aligned}$$

This shows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 E &= \prod_{j=1}^r H_j \quad \text{if } r \text{ is even and,} \\
 E &= \{\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*, \left(\frac{a}{l_1}\right) = \dots = \left(\frac{a}{l_r}\right)\} \quad \text{if } r \text{ is odd.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Suppose that $H = \prod_{i=1}^{r_2} U_i$ where U_i is a subgroup of $(\mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z})^*$ for $i = 1, \dots, r_2$. Let $h = (a + p_1\mathbb{Z}, \dots, a + p_{r_2}\mathbb{Z})$ be an element of H such that $\left(\frac{a}{p_1}\right) = \left(\frac{a}{p_2}\right) = -1$ and $\left(\frac{a}{p_i}\right) = 1$ for $i > 2$. Let $\hat{h} = (a + p_1\mathbb{Z}, a^2 + p_2\mathbb{Z}, a + p_3\mathbb{Z}, \dots, a + p_{r_2}\mathbb{Z})$. Since we get \hat{h} from h by squaring one of its components, then, on one hand $\hat{h} \in H$. On the other hand, $\left(\frac{a}{p_1}\right) \left(\frac{a^2}{p_2}\right) \left(\frac{a}{p_3}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{p_{r_2}}\right) = -1$, so that $\hat{h} \notin H$, a contradiction. The proof of the relation of inclusion between the groups E and F is obvious and will be omitted. □

3 Factorization of Carmichael numbers.

Let n be a Carmichael number. We say that it is a really strong Carmichael number if $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$, for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. The study of this class of numbers will be done in Sections 5 and 6.

Theorem 4. *Let n be a Carmichael number, not really strong. Let A (resp. B) be the set of prime factors l (resp. p) of n such that $\nu_2(l-1) = \nu_2(n-1)$ (resp. $\nu_2(p-1) < \nu_2(n-1)$). Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ be such that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. Partition A in the form $A = A_1(a) \cup A_2(a)$, where $A_1(a) = \{l \in A, \left(\frac{a}{l}\right) = 1\}$ and $A_2(a) = \{l \in A, \left(\frac{a}{l}\right) = -1\}$. Then $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n) = \prod_{p \in B} p \prod_{l \in A_1(a)} l$ and $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} + 1, n) = \prod_{l \in A_2(a)} l$ where, by convention, if B or $A_1(a)$ or $A_2(a)$ is empty, then the corresponding product is equal to 1. In particular, if a modulo t is primitive root of unity in $\mathbb{Z}/t\mathbb{Z}$ for any prime factor t of n , then $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n) = \prod_{p \in B} p$ and $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} + 1, n) = \prod_{l \in A} l$.*

Proof. The assumption n is not really strong means that there exists $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $a^{(n-1)/2} - 1 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{n}$. Let $p \in B$. Since $\nu_2(p-1) \leq \nu_2((n-1)/2)$, then $p-1 \mid (n-1)/2$. Set $(n-1)/2 = (p-1)q$, where q is a positive integer. Then $a^{(n-1)/2} = a^{(p-1)q} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, so that $p \mid a^{(n-1)/2} - 1$.

Let $l \in A$, then $\nu_2(l-1) = \nu_2(n-1)$, hence $(n-1)/2 \equiv (l-1)/2 \pmod{l-1}$. Set $(n-1)/2 = (l-1)/2 + (l-1)y$, where y is a positive integer. Then by Euler's criterion,

$$\begin{aligned}
 a^{(n-1)/2} &= a^{(l-1)/2} a^{(l-1)y} \\
 &\equiv a^{(l-1)/2} \pmod{l} \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{a}{l}\right) \pmod{l} \\
 &\equiv \begin{cases} 1 \pmod{l} & \text{if } l \in A_1(a) \\ -1 \pmod{l} & \text{if } l \in A_2(a). \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

We proved that any $p \in B$ divides the integer $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n)$. An element $l \in A$ divides this integer if and only if $l \in A_1(a)$. Since n is square-free, so is this \gcd and the formula for the first \gcd is established.

The above congruences of $a^{(n-1)/2}$ modulo l for l in A shows that $l \mid a^{(n-1)/2} + 1$ for any l in $A_2(a)$. Since these primes are factors of n , they divide $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} + 1, n)$. The other prime factors of n are not divisors of this second \gcd , since they divide the first and they are odd, so $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} + 1, n) = \prod_{l \in A_2(a)} l$.

We prove the last sentence of Theorem 4. For the first \gcd , it is sufficient to show that $A_1(a) = \emptyset$. If $l \in A_1(a)$, then $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{l}\right) \pmod{l} \equiv 1 \pmod{l}$, hence a is a square in $(\mathbb{Z}/l\mathbb{Z})^*$, which is a contradiction. Thus, $A_1(a)$ is empty. This implies $A_2(a) = A$ and $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} + 1, n) = \prod_{l \in A} l$. □

Corollary 1. *Let n be a positive odd composite number. Then n is a Carmichael*

number if and only if, for any integer a such that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, we have

$$\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n)\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} + 1, n) = n. \quad (1)$$

Proof. The necessity of the condition is obvious if n is really strong and follows from the preceding theorem otherwise. We prove the sufficiency of the condition. Let t be a prime number such that $t^e \mid n$, ($e \geq 1$). Since these \gcd 's are coprime, then for any a , $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, $t^e \mid \gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - \epsilon_a, n)$ where $\epsilon_a = \pm 1$, hence $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \epsilon_a \pmod{t^e}$. Thus, $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{t^e}$ for any a with $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. This implies $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ for any a , $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, which means that n is a Carmichael number. □

Definition 1. Let n be a Carmichael number and $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. Suppose that $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n) \notin \{1, n\}$, then Equation (1) implies that we may factorize properly n . In this case, we say that a properly factorize n .

Corollary 2. Let n be a Carmichael number not really strong, A and B as in Theorem 4, $r_1 = |A|$, $r_2 = |B|$ and $r = r_1 + r_2$. Then the proportion of integers $a \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, such that a properly factorize n , is equal to $1 - 1/2^{r-1}$ if $B = \emptyset$ and $1 - 1/2^{r_1}$ if $B \neq \emptyset$. In the two cases, this proportion is at least equal to $1/2$.

Proof. We first count those $a \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$ which do not allow the factorization of n . For these elements, we have $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n) = 1$ or $\gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n) = n$. The first case holds only if $B = \emptyset$.

We will use the following properties. Since $t - 1 \mid n - 1$ for any prime factor t of n , then for any $p_i \in B$ ($1 \leq i \leq r_2$) and any $l_j \in A$ ($1 \leq j \leq r_1$), we have $p_i - 1 \mid (n - 1)/2$ and $(n - 1)/2 \equiv (l_j - 1)/2 \pmod{l_j - 1}$. By Euler's criterion, this implies

$$a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i} \quad \text{and} \quad a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv a^{(l_j-1)/2} \pmod{l_j} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) \pmod{l_j} \quad (2)$$

for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$.

Let

$$C_1 = \{\bar{a} \in \{1, \dots, n - 1\}, \gcd(a, n) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n) = n\}$$

and

$$C_2 = \{\bar{a} \in \{1, \dots, n - 1\}, \gcd(a, n) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \gcd(a^{(n-1)/2} - 1, n) = 1\}.$$

The sets B , $A_1(a)$ and $A_2(a)$ which occur in this proof are defined as the preceding theorem.

• **The cardinality of C_1 .** For any $a \in C_1$, we have $A_2(a) = \emptyset$ and $A_1(a) = B \neq \emptyset$.

Let $a \in \{1, \dots, n - 1\}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, then by (2) $a \in C_1$ if and only if $\left(\frac{a}{l_j}\right) = 1$ for $j = 1, \dots, r_1$. This shows that

$$C_1 = \begin{cases} (\mathbb{Z}/l_1\mathbb{Z})^{*2} \times \dots \times (\mathbb{Z}/l_r\mathbb{Z})^{*2} & \text{if } B = \emptyset \\ (\mathbb{Z}/p_1\mathbb{Z})^* \times \dots \times (\mathbb{Z}/p_{r_2}\mathbb{Z})^* \times (\mathbb{Z}/l_1\mathbb{Z})^{*2} \times \dots \times (\mathbb{Z}/l_{r_1}\mathbb{Z})^{*2} & \text{if } B \neq \emptyset. \end{cases}$$

This shows that $|C_1| = \Phi(n)/2^r$ if $B = \emptyset$ and $|C_1| = \Phi(n)/2^{r_1}$ if $B \neq \emptyset$.

• **The cardinality of C_2 .** Notice that $C_2 \neq \emptyset$ if and only if $B = \emptyset$. Suppose that $B = \emptyset$ and let $a \in C_2$, then $A_1(a) = \emptyset$ and $A_2(a) = A$. By (2), $\left(\frac{a}{t}\right) = -1$ for any prime factor t of n , thus $C_2 = \{a \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}, \gcd(a, n) = 1, \left(\frac{a}{t_i}\right) = -1, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, r\}$. This shows that $|C_2| = \Phi(n)/2^r$.

We deduce that the number of a 's which do not allow the factorisation of n is equal to $|C_1| + |C_2| = \Phi(n)/2^{r-1}$ (resp. $|C_1| = \Phi(n)/2^{r_1}$) if $B = \emptyset$ (resp. $B \neq \emptyset$). This implies that the proportion of the a 's not allowing the factorization of n is equal to $1/2^{r-1}$ if $B = \emptyset$ and $1/2^{r_1}$ if $B \neq \emptyset$. Then the number of a 's which allow the factorization of n is equal to $1 - 1/2^{r-1}$ if $B = \emptyset$ and $1 - 1/2^{r_1}$ if $B \neq \emptyset$.

If $B = \emptyset$, since $r \geq 3$, then $1 - 1/2^{r-1} \geq 3/4$. If $B \neq \emptyset$, then $r_1 \geq 1$, thus $1 - 1/2^{r_1} \geq 1/2$. This shows that the proportion of integers $a \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, which allows the factorization of integers is at least equal to $1/2$. \square

4 On a theorem of Frobenius and on Lehmer's problem

Theorem 5. *Let G be a finite group, m be a positive integer and $A_m(G) = \{x \in G, x^m = e\}$. Then $|A_m(G)|$ is a multiple of $\gcd(m, |G|)$.*

Proof. [5] or [9]. □

Notice that $A_m(G) = A_{\gcd(m, |G|)}$. We apply this theorem to the case $G = (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$, where n is a Carmichael number and $m = (n - 1)/2$. In this case $A_m(G) = F$ and by Theorem 3, $|F| = \Phi(n)/2^{r_1}$. Hence, $|F| = \phi(n)/2^{r_1} = \gcd(\Phi(n), (n - 1)/2)q(n)$, where $q(n)$ is a positive integer. This identity shows that any divisor of $q(n)$ divides $\Phi(n)$.

In what follows, we discuss the possibility for $q(n)$ to be equal to 1.

Theorem 6. *Let n be a Carmichael number and F be the group defined above. Let $d = \gcd((n - 1)/2, \Phi(n))$ and $q(n)$ be the positive integer such that $|F| = dq(n)$. Let $\{t_0, t_1, \dots, t_s\}$ be the set of prime factors of $\lambda(n)$ with $t_0 = 2$. Set*

$$\Phi(n) = \prod_{i=0}^s t_i^{u_i} \quad \text{and} \quad (n - 1)/2 = \prod_{i=0}^s t_i^{v_i} z,$$

where z is a positive integer coprime to t_i for $i = 0, \dots, s$.

If $r_1 = 0$, then

$$q(n) = \begin{cases} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i - v_i} & \text{if } u_0 \leq v_0 \\ 2^{u_0 - v_0} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i - v_i} & \text{if } u_0 > v_0. \end{cases}$$

If $r_1 \neq 0$, then

$$q(n) = 2^{u_0 - r_1 - v_0} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i - v_i}.$$

Proof. Since $|F| = \Phi(n)/2^{r_1}$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 |F| &= 2^{u_0-r_1} \prod_{i=1}^s t_i^{u_i} \\
 &= 2^{u_0-r_1} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i \leq v_i}} t_i^{u_i} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i} \\
 &= 2^{u_0-r_1} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i \leq v_i}} t_i^{u_i} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{v_i} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i-v_i}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We distinguish two cases: $r_1 = 0$ and $r_1 \neq 0$.

Case 1: $r_1 = 0$. We have $u_0 = \nu_2(\Phi(n)) = \nu_1 + \dots + \nu_{r_2}$, $v_0 = \nu_2((n-1)/2)$ and $u_0 - r_1 = u_0$.

Subcase a: $u_0 \leq v_0$. In this case, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 |F| &= 2^{\nu_2(d)} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i \leq v_i}} t_i^{u_i} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{v_i} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i-v_i} \\
 &= d \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i-v_i},
 \end{aligned}$$

hence $q(n) = \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i-v_i}$.

Subcase b: $u_0 > v_0$. We have $u_0 = v_0 + (u_0 - v_0)$, hence

$$\begin{aligned}
 |F| &= (2^{\nu_2(d)} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i \leq v_i}} t_i^{u_i} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{v_i}) (2^{u_0-v_0} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i-v_i}) \\
 &= d 2^{u_0-v_0} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i-v_i},
 \end{aligned}$$

thus $q(n) = 2^{u_0-v_0} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i-v_i}$.

Case 2: $r_1 \neq 0$. We have $u_0 = \nu_1 + \cdots + \nu_{r_2} + r_1\nu$, $u_0 - r_1 = \nu_1 + \cdots + \nu_{r_2} + r_1(\nu - 1)$ and $v_0 = \nu_2((n - 1)/2) = \nu - 1$. If $u_0 \leq v_0$, then $\nu_1 + \cdots + \nu_{r_2} + r_1\nu \leq \nu - 1$, hence $\nu_1 + \cdots + \nu_{r_2} + (r_1 - 1)\nu \leq -1$, which is impossible since $r_1 \geq 1$. We deduce that necessarily $u_0 > v_0$. Write $u_0 - r_1$ in the form $u_0 - r_1 = (u_0 - r_1 - v_0) + v_0$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} |F| &= (2^{\nu_2(d)} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i \leq v_i}} t_i^{u_i} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{v_i}) (2^{u_0 - r_1 - v_0} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i - v_i}) \\ &= d2^{u_0 - r_1 - v_0} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i - v_i}, \end{aligned}$$

hence $q(n) = 2^{u_0 - r_1 - v_0} \prod_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq s \\ u_i > v_i}} t_i^{u_i - v_i}$. □

Let n be a positive integer. It is well known and easy to prove that n is a prime number if and only if $\Phi(n) = n - 1$. In 1932, Lehmer asked the question: Do there exist composite integers n such that $\Phi(n) \mid n - 1$ [10]. This is now called Lehmer's problem. G. E. Pinch stated that the number of primes factors of a composite integer n satisfying this Lehmer's condition must be at least 15 and that there is no such number less than 10^{30} .

Corollary 3. *Let n be a Carmichael number and F be the group defined above. Let $d = \gcd((n - 1)/2, \Phi(n))$ and $q(n)$ be the positive integer such that $|F| = dq(n)$. Then $q(n) \neq 1$ except if $r_2 = 0$ and $\nu = 1$ or $r_1 = 0$ and $u_0 \leq v_0$. If $r_2 = 0$ and $\nu\nu_2((n - 1)/2) = 1$ (which is equivalent to $n \equiv -1 \pmod{4}$), then we may have $q(n) = 1$. If $r_1 = 0$ and $u_0 \leq v_0$ and the Lehmer's problem has no solution, then $q(n) \neq 1$ in this case.*

Proof. Suppose first that $r_1 \neq 0$. We look at the exponent of 2 in $q(n)$, showed in Theorem 6, and we want it to be non-zero, that is $u_0 - r_1 - v_0 \neq 0$. We have $u_0 - r_1 - v_0 = \nu_1 + \cdots + \nu_{r_2} + \nu r_1 - r_1 - (\nu - 1) = \nu_1 + \cdots + \nu_{r_2} + (r_1 - 1)(\nu - 1)$ and this vanishes if and only if $r_2 = 0$ and $\nu = 1$. If one of these conditions does not hold, then $q(n) \neq 1$. Suppose next that $r_1 = 0$. Theorem 6, again, proves the corollary in the case $u_0 > v_0$. It remains to consider the case $r_1 = 0$ and $u_0 \leq v_0$. In this case, we have $\Phi(n) = |F| = dq(n) = \gcd(\Phi(n), (n-1)/2)q(n)$. If $q(n) = 1$, then $\Phi(n) \mid n-1$ and the condition of Lehmer is satisfied for the composite integer n . \square

Remark 1. *Let n be a Carmichael number. Corollary 3 shows that if $q(n) = 1$, then either*

(i) $r_1 = 0$ and $u_0 \leq v_0$ or

(ii) $r_2 = 0$ and $\nu = 1$, equivalently $n \equiv -1 \pmod{4}$.

Suppose that $q(n) = 1$ and (i) holds, then $\Phi(n) = \gcd(\Phi(n), (n-1)/2)$, hence $\phi(n) \mid (n-1)/2$, thus $\phi(n) \mid n-1$. This implies that n is a Lehmer number. Suppose next that $q(n) = 1$ and (ii) holds, then $\Phi(n)/2^{r_1} = \gcd(\Phi(n), (n-1)/2)$, hence $\Phi(n)/2^{r_1-1} \mid n-1$, that is $\Phi(n) \mid 2^{r_1-1}(n-1)$ and we are led to a condition close to that of Lehmer. But here $n = 8911 = 7 \times 19 \times 67$ satisfies this condition. Indeed, it is the unique Carmichael number which does this among the 10000 first Carmichael numbers listed in [6].

5 Really strong Carmichael numbers.

Let n be a Carmichael number and $e(n) = \nu_2(n - 1) \geq 1$. For any k , $1 \leq k \leq e(n)$, we consider the condition

$$(C_k) \quad a^{(n-1)/2^k} \equiv 1 \pmod{n} \quad \text{for any } a \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad \gcd(a, n) = 1.$$

It is clear that if (C_k) is satisfied, then all the conditions $(C_k), (C_{k-1}), \dots, (C_1)$ are verified. A number n which satisfies (C_k) for some $1 \leq k \leq e(n)$, hence for $k = 1$, will be called a really strong Carmichael number. We will show that contrary to strong Carmichael numbers, really strong Carmichael numbers exist.

Notice that, since the exponent of the group $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ is equal to $\lambda(n)$, then the condition (C_k) is equivalent to $\lambda(n) \mid (n - 1)/2^k$.

Proposition 1. *Let n be a Carmichael number. If $n \equiv -1 \pmod{4}$, then any prime factor of n is congruent to -1 modulo 4 and the number of these primes is odd. Moreover, n is not really strong.*

Proof. Since $n \equiv -1 \pmod{4}$, then $n - 1 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. Let p be a prime factor of n . Since p is odd and $p - 1 \mid n - 1$, then $p - 1 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, hence $p \equiv -1 \pmod{4}$. Let r be the number of prime factors of n , then $-1 \equiv n \pmod{4} \equiv (-1)^r \pmod{4}$, hence r is odd. Now $(n - 1)/2$ is odd and $\lambda(n)$ is even, hence $\lambda(n) \nmid (n - 1)/2$ and n is not really strong. \square

Example. The integer $n = 8911 = 7 \times 19 \times 67$ satisfies the conditions of this

proposition.

By the Main Theorem in [12], there are infinitely many integers n satisfying the conditions of this proposition.

Theorem 7. *Let $n \geq 3$ be an odd integer and k be an integer such that $1 \leq k \leq e(n)$.*

1. *The following conditions are equivalent.*

(i) *n is a prime number or a Carmichael number.*

(ii) *For any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, we have $\overline{a^{(n-1)/2^k}}$ is a 2^k -th root of 1 in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$.*

2. *Suppose that n satisfies the above equivalent conditions. Let A_k be the set of prime numbers p dividing n such that $\nu_2(p-1) > \nu_2((n-1)/2^k)$.*

Let $\theta : (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^ \rightarrow (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ be the map such that $\theta(\bar{x}) = \overline{x^{(n-1)/2^k}}$. Then θ is a homomorphism of groups and*

$$\text{Im}\theta \simeq \prod_{p_i \in A_k} (\mathbb{F}_{p_i}^*)^{u_i} \simeq \prod_{p_i \in A_k} \{2^{s_i}\text{-th roots of } 1 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z}\} \simeq \prod_{p_i \in A_k} \langle \xi_i^{(p_i-1)/2^{s_i}} \rangle,$$

where ξ_i is a generator of $(\mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z})^$, $s_i = \nu_2(p_i-1) - (e-k)$ and $u_i = (p_i-1)/2^{s_i}$.*

Moreover,

$$\text{Im}\theta = \{\bar{x} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^* \mid x \equiv 1 \text{ or } x^{2^k} \equiv 1 \pmod{p} \text{ according to } p \notin A_k \text{ or } p \in A_k\}.$$

Proof. 1. • (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ be such that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$ and let $b = a^{(n-1)/2^k}$.

Since $\overline{a^{n-1}} = \bar{1}$, then $\overline{b^{2^k}} = \overline{a^{(n-1)/2^k \cdot 2^k}} = \overline{a^{n-1}} = \bar{1}$, hence b is a 2^k -th root of 1 modulo n .

• (ii) \Rightarrow (i). Suppose that n is not a prime number, that is n is composite. Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, then $\bar{1} = \overline{a^{(n-1)/2^k 2^k}} = \overline{a^{n-1}}$, hence n is a Carmichael number.

2. Obviously, θ is a homomorphism of groups. We compute the image of θ . We will use the following:

Claim. Let p be a prime divisor of n , then $p - 1 \mid (n - 1)/2^k$ if and only if $p \notin A_k$.

Proof. For any odd prime t , we have $\nu_t((n - 1)/2^k) = \nu_t(n - 1)$, hence

$$\begin{aligned} p - 1 \mid (n - 1)/2^k &\Leftrightarrow \nu_l(p - 1) \leq \nu_l((n - 1)/2^k) \quad \text{for any prime } l \\ &\Leftrightarrow \nu_2(p - 1) \leq \nu_2((n - 1)/2^k) = \nu_2(n - 1) - k \\ &\Leftrightarrow p \notin A_k. \end{aligned}$$

This claim being proved, let $\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a} \in \text{Ker}\theta &\Leftrightarrow \overline{a^{(n-1)/2^k}} = \bar{1} \\ &\Leftrightarrow a^{(n-1)/2^k} \equiv 1 \pmod{p} \quad \text{for any } p \mid n \\ &\Leftrightarrow (\text{ by the claim}) \quad a^{(n-1)/2^k} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i} \quad \text{for } p_i \in A_k. \end{aligned}$$

For i such that $p_i \in A_k$, let $\xi_i \in \mathbb{Z}$ be such that its reduction modulo p_i is a

primitive p_i -th root of unity and let u_i be such that $a \equiv \xi_i^{u_i} \pmod{p_i}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} a^{(n-1)/2^k} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i} &\Leftrightarrow \xi_i^{u_i(n-1)/2^k} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i} \\ &\Leftrightarrow p_i - 1 \mid u_i(n-1)/2^k \\ &\Leftrightarrow \nu_2(p_i - 1) \leq \nu_2(u_i(n-1)/2^k) \\ &= \nu_2(u_i) + \nu_2((n-1)/2^k) \end{aligned}$$

Since $\nu_2(p_i - 1) > \nu_2((n-1)/2^k) = e - k$, set $\nu_2(p_i - 1) = e - k + s_i$, where s_i is a positive integer. Then

$$\begin{aligned} p_i - 1 \mid u_i(n-1)/2^k &\Leftrightarrow e - k + s_i \leq \nu_2(u_i) + e - k \\ &\Leftrightarrow \nu_2(u_i) \geq s_i. \end{aligned}$$

We deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{a} \in \text{Ker}\theta &\Leftrightarrow \nu_2(u_i) \geq s_i = \nu_2(p_i - 1) - (e - k) \quad \text{for } p_i \in A_k \\ &\Leftrightarrow 2^{s_i} \mid u_i \quad \text{for } p_i \in A_k \\ &\Leftrightarrow a \text{ modulo } p_i \text{ is a } 2^{s_i} \text{-th power in } \mathbb{Z}/p_i\mathbb{Z} \quad \text{for } p_i \in A_k. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\text{Ker}\theta \simeq \left(\prod_{p_i \notin A_k} \mathbb{F}_{p_i}^*\right) \times \left(\prod_{p_j \in A_k} \mathbb{F}_{p_j}^{*2^{s_j}}\right)$.

This implies that

$$\begin{aligned}
 Im\theta &\simeq \prod_{p_j \in A_k} (\mathbb{F}_{p_j}^*)^{v_j} \\
 &\simeq \prod_{p_j \in A_k} \{2^{s_j}\text{-th roots of } 1 \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}/p_j\mathbb{Z}\} \\
 &\simeq \prod_{p_j \in A_k} \langle \xi_j^{(p_j-1)/2^{s_j}} \rangle,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $v_j = (p_j - 1)/2^{s_j}$. Moreover,

$$Im\theta = \{\bar{x} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^* \mid x \equiv 1 \text{ or } x^{2^k} \equiv 1 \pmod{p} \text{ according to } p \notin A_k \text{ or } p \in A_k\}.$$

□

6 The role of the square roots of 1.

Theorem 7 shows that if n is a prime number or a Carmichael number, then as a runs over \mathbb{Z} and $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, $a^{(n-1)/2}$ takes $2^{|A_1|}$ distinct values modulo n , all of them being square roots of 1.

Corollary 4. *Let $n \geq 3$ be an odd integer and*

$$V = \{\overline{a^{(n-1)/2}}, a \in \mathbb{Z}, \gcd(a, n) = 1\} \subset (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$$

1. *V contains an element which is not a square root of 1 if and only if n is not prime nor a Carmichael number.*

2. If all the elements of V are square roots of 1, then n is a prime number if and only if $V = \{-1, 1\}$.

Proof. 1. Suppose that all the elements of V are square roots of 1. Then for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, we have $a^{n-1} = 1$, hence n is a prime or a Carmichael number. The converse is obvious by Fermat small theorem and by the very definition of Carmichael numbers.

2. Suppose $n = p$ is a prime number and let $x = \overline{a^{(n-1)/2}} = \overline{a^{(p-1)/2}} \in V$, then $x^2 = \overline{a^{p-1}} = \bar{1}$, hence $x = \pm 1$.

Conversely, suppose that $V = \{-1, 1\}$. Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ be such that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. Since $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{n}$, then $a^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. By 1., n is a prime or a Carmichael number. We must eliminate the second possibility. Let A_1 (resp. B_1) be the set (possibly empty) of prime numbers p , $p \mid n$ such that $\nu_2(p-1) = \nu_2(n-1)$ (resp. $\nu_2(p-1) < \nu_2(n-1)$). Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$ such that $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{n}$. Then for any $p \in B_1$, $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$, which is a contradiction, thus $B_1 = \emptyset$. Let l_1, \dots, l_r be the elements of A_1 . Set $n-1 = (l_i-1)q_i$, where q_i is an odd integer. Let a_1, \dots, a_r be integers such that $a_1^{(l_1-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{l_1}$ and $a_i^{(l_i-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{l_i}$ for $i = 2, \dots, r$. Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ be such that $a \equiv a_i \pmod{l_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$. We have $a_1^{(n-1)/2} = a_1^{q_1(l_1-1)/2} \equiv (-1)^{q_1} \pmod{l_1} \equiv -1 \pmod{l_1}$ and $a^{(n-1)/2} = a_i^{q_i(l_i-1)/2} \equiv 1^q \pmod{l_i} \equiv 1 \pmod{l_i}$ for $i = 2, \dots, r$, hence $a^{(n-1)/2} \not\equiv \pm 1 \pmod{n}$.

□

Example. Let $n = 3367$, then $(n - 1)/2 = 1683$, $2^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1807 \pmod{n}$ and $1807^2 \equiv 2626 \pmod{n} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{n}$, hence by Corollary 4, n is not a prime nor a Carmichael number.

Remark 2. *If all the elements of V are square roots of 1, then by 1., n is a prime number or a Carmichael number, thus item 2. of the above corollary may be replaced by the following:*

If all the elements of V are square roots of 1, then n is a Carmichael number if and only if $V \neq \{-1, 1\}$.

Notice that if $a^{(n-1)/2}$ is a square root of 1 for any $\bar{a} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$, then the set V is a subgroup of the group S of square roots of unity, so $\{1\} \subset V \subset S \subset (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$.

Corollary 5. *Let $n = p_1 \cdots p_r$ be a square-free integer such that all the elements of V are square roots of 1. Let r_2 (resp. r_1) be the number of p_i 's such that $\nu_2(p_i - 1) < \nu_2(n - 1)$ (resp. $\nu_2(p_i - 1) = \nu_2(n - 1)$). Then the first three (resp. the last three) following conditions are equivalent.*

(i) $r_1 = 0$.

(ii) $V = \{1\}$.

(iii) n is really strong.

(iv) $r_2 = 0$.

(v) $-1 \in V$.

(vi) $V = \{\bar{x} \in (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^* \mid \bar{x}^2 = 1\}$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Since for any $i = 1, \dots, r$, $\nu_2(p_i - 1) < \nu_2(n - 1)$, then $\nu_2(p_i - 1) \leq \nu_2((n - 1)/2)$, hence $p_i - 1 \mid (n - 1)/2$. Since for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, we have $a^{p_i-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$, then $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. This implies $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$ for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. Therefore, $V = \{1\}$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). Obvious.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i). By contradiction, suppose that there exists $i \in \{1, \dots, r\}$ such that $\nu_2(p_i - 1) = \nu_2(n - 1)$. Since $p_i - 1 \mid n - 1$, then we may set $n - 1 = (p_i - 1)q$, where q is an odd integer. Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $a^{(p_i-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_i}$, then $a^{(n-1)/2} = (a^{(p_i-1)/2})^q \equiv (-1)^q \pmod{p_i} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_i}$, hence $a^{(n-1)/2} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{n}$, which is a contradiction.

(iv) \Rightarrow (v). For any $i = 1, \dots, r$, $\nu_2(p_i - 1) = \nu_2(n - 1)$, hence $n - 1 = (p_i - 1)q_i$, where q_i is an odd positive integer. For $i = 1, \dots, r$, let $a_i \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $a_i^{(p_i-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_i}$. By the Chinese remainder theorem, let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $a \equiv a_i \pmod{p_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$. Then $a^{(p_i-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$. Hence $a^{(n-1)/2} = (a^{(p_i-1)/2})^{q_i} \equiv (-1)^{q_i} \pmod{p_i} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$, thus $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{n}$. This implies $-1 \in V$.

(v) \Rightarrow (vi). By assumption, any element of V is a square root of 1. We show the

converse. Let $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ be a fixed integer such that $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{n}$, then for $i = 1, \dots, r$, $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{p_i}$. Let \bar{x} be a square root of 1 in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, then x is a square root of 1 modulo p_i for $i = 1, \dots, r$, hence $x \equiv \epsilon_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$, where $\epsilon_i = \pm 1$. Set

$$b_i = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } \epsilon_i = -1 \\ \epsilon_i & \text{if } \epsilon_i = 1 \end{cases}$$

and let $b \in \mathbb{Z}$ be such that $b \equiv b_i \pmod{p_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, r$. Then $b^{(n-1)/2} \in V$ and

$$\begin{aligned} b^{(n-1)/2} &\equiv b_i^{(n-1)/2} \pmod{p_i} \\ &\equiv \epsilon_i \pmod{p_i} \\ &\equiv x \pmod{p_i}. \end{aligned}$$

(vi) \Rightarrow (iv). Since $\overline{-1} \in V$, then there exists $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{n}$. This implies that $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$ for any prime factor p of n . We deduce that $p-1 \nmid (n-1)/2$, and since $p-1 \mid n-1$, then $\nu_2(p-1) = \nu_2(n-1)$. Therefore, $r_2 = 0$. □

Corollary 6. *Let n be a Carmichael number for which $r_2 \neq 0$, then for any $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, we have $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{n}$ if and only if $a^{(n-1)/2} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$.*

Proof. The sufficiency of the condition is obvious. We prove the necessity, that is $a^{(n-1)/2} \not\equiv -1 \pmod{n}$. This is true by the preceding equivalence of (iv) and (v) and by our assumption $r_2 \neq 0$. □

Here is the list of the sixteen first Carmichael numbers n with the factorizations of n and $n - 1$ along with the values of $\lambda(n)$ and (r_1, r_2) .

n	$n - 1$	$\lambda(n)$	(r_1, r_2)
561=3.11.17	560 = $2^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 7$	$\lambda(561) = 2^4 \cdot 5$	(1, 2)
1105=5.13.17	1104 = $2^4 \cdot 3 \cdot 23$	$\lambda(1105) = 2^4 \cdot 3$	(1, 2)
1729=7.13.19	1728 = $2^6 \cdot 3^3$	$\lambda(1729) = 2^2 \cdot 3^2$	(0, 3)
2465=5.17.29	2464 = $2^5 \cdot 7 \cdot 11$	$\lambda(2465) = 2^4 \cdot 7$	(0, 3)
2821=7.13.31	2820 = $2^2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 47$	$\lambda(2821) = 2^2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5$	(1, 2)
6601=7.23.41	6600 = $2^3 \cdot 3 \cdot 5^2 \cdot 11$	$\lambda(6601) = 2^3 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 11$	(1, 2)
8911=7.19.67.	8910 = $2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 11$	$\lambda(8911) = 2 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 11$	(3, 0)
10585=5.29.73	10584 = $2^3 \cdot 3^3 \cdot 7^2$	$\lambda(10585) = 2^3 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 7$	(1, 2)
15841=7.31.73	15840 = $2^5 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 5 \cdot 11$	$\lambda(15841) = 2^3 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 5$	(0, 3)
29341=13.37.61.	29340 = $2^2 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 5 \cdot 163$	$\lambda(29341) = 2^2 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 5$	(3, 0)
41041=7.11.13.41	41040 = $2^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 5 \cdot 19$	$\lambda(41041) = 2^3 \cdot 3 \cdot 5$	(0, 4)
46657=13.37.97	46656 = $2^6 \cdot 3^6$	$\lambda(46657) = 2^5 \cdot 3^2$	(0, 3)
52633=7.73.103	52632 = $2^3 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 17 \cdot 43$	$\lambda(52633) = 2^3 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 17$	(1, 2)
62745=3.5.47.89.	62744 = $2^3 \cdot 11 \cdot 23 \cdot 31$	$\lambda(62745) = 2^3 \cdot 11 \cdot 23$	(1, 3)
63973=7.13.19.37	63972 = $2^2 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 1777$	$\lambda(63973) = 2^2 \cdot 3^2$	(2, 2)
75361=11.13.17.31.	75360 = $2^5 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 157$	$\lambda(75361) = 2^4 \cdot 3 \cdot 5$	(0, 4)

Among these Carmichael numbers, six of them are really strong Carmichael numbers,

namely: 1729, 2465, 15841, 41041, 46657, 75361. Clearly, if $n \equiv -1 \pmod{4}$, then by Proposition 1, $r_2 = 0$ and $r_1 = r$. The converse is false, as is shown by the number $n = 29341 = 13 \times 37 \times 61$ contained in the above table. Notice that in this table there is no number for which $(r_1, r_2) = (2, 1)$.

Question. Given non-negative integers r_1, r_2, r , such that $r \geq 3$ and $r_1 + r_2 = r$, can one find a Carmichael number n such that n has r prime factors, r_2 of them say p_1, \dots, p_{r_2} satisfy the condition $\nu_2(p_i - 1) < \nu_2(n - 1)$ and the remaining ones p_{r_2+1}, \dots, p_r verify the condition $\nu_2(p_j - 1) = \nu_2(n - 1)$?

References

- [1] W. R. Alford, A. Granville, C. Pomerance, There are infinitely many Carmichael numbers, *Annals of Math.* 140, (1994) 703-722.
- [2] R. D. Carmichael, Note on a new number theory function, *Bull. A. M. S.* 16 (1910) 232-238.
- [3] R. D. Carmichael, On composite numbers P which satisfy the Fermat congruence $a^{P-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{P}$, *Amer. Math. Monthly*, 19((1912) 22-27.
- [4] H. Davenport, *The higher arithmetic*, fifth edition, Cambridge University Press,((1982).

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- [5] F. G. Frobenius, Verallgemeinerung des Sylowschen Satzes, Berliner Sitz, (11895), 981-993.
- [6] <http://www.oeis.org/A002997/b002997.txt>
- [7] B. C. Kellner, J. Sondow, On Carmichael and polygonal numbers, Bernoulli polynomials, and sums of base-p digits, *Integers*. 21 (2021) A52, 1-21.
- [8] A. R. Korselt, Problème chinois, *L'intermédiaire des mathématiciens* 6 (1899) 142-143.
- [9] D. Khurana, A. Khurana, A Theorem of Frobenius and its Applications, *Mathematics Magazine*. 78, (2005) 220-225.
- [10] D. H. Lehmer, On Euler's totient function, *Bull. A. M. S.* 38 (1932) 745-757.
- [11] D. H. Lehmer, Strong Carmichael numbers, *J. Aust. Math. Soc.* 21 (1976) 508-510.
- [12] T. Wright, Infinitely many Carmichael numbers in arithmetic progressions, *Bull. London Math. Soc.* 45 (2013) 943-952.